

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE ROLES OF PRIESTHOOD IN AFRICAN TRADITIONAL RELIGION AND CHRISTIANITY

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ABSTRACT

Priesthood in both African Traditional Religion and Christianity is seen as fulfilling the same goal, but from different perspectives/dimensions. A priest is a person appointed/anointed to perform religious duties and ceremonies in a specific way/manner. Existing studies have examined issues such as ordination, conflict resolution, church administration, and others, with meagre attention to the similarity in priesthood in Christianity and African Traditional Religion. This study thus explains such similarities with a view to examining their social and religious ideals in the present age. Qualitative and comparative methodologies were employed in this study, which involved both oral interviews and the examination of library materials.

It has been discovered that there is bias against African Traditional Religion by Christians, as they tag everything African as evil and their religion as authentic and the only religion, claiming that without accepting Christ, heaven is not certain for them. It is not everything about Christianity, and ATR is perfect. So condemnation of one another's religion is an albatross. However, observers in the traditional priesthood see the priest as crooked and tattered because of their appearance: wearing tattered clothes and carrying dirty bags, which makes them feared by people. This leads to a perception that they are perpetrators of evil in the community. Nollywood people also portray them in bad manners. Some scholars who have carried out research equally were subjective in their ideas without proving that there is a meeting point between the two religions. Since there is a slight variance between the two religions, they should ensure coexistence among them. Both faiths should incorporate good ideas from each other. It is therefore advised that both Christianity and African Traditional Religion should find a meeting point for quality growth in the religious space.

Keywords: Comparative, Roles, Priesthood, ATR, Christianity

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

The noun priest refers to a person appointed to perform religious duties and ceremonies in the Roman Catholic, Orthodox, or mainstream Protestant Churches. A priest used in the above sense in this study is an empowered layperson, who by ordination is called to the ministry of the gospel of Jesus Christ, the High Priest, and also in African traditional religion. The term Priesthood is one of the oldest institutions of humanity all over the world. The reason is undoubtedly linked to the religious inclinations of humans. Man, however, is spiritual by nature, "Homo Religiosus". Man's preoccupation with the Sacred, which Rudolf Otto described as... "A mystery inexpressible and above creatures"¹. *Mysterium tremendum*. – a mystery which attracts and repels, must have accelerated the growth of the priesthood in human society. So many social scientists are not deluded in classifying religion as one of the five social institutions of humanity².

By social institutions we mean... "a complex or cluster of roles, which are knit together for accomplishment of given ends..."³ In the religious sphere, communication with the sacred is often through holy rites, and the maintenance of the sacred order within the various spheres of human activities has become an essential aspect of any society.

Emil Durkheim⁴ Indeed, it claims that this equates religion with a divinized society. However, in its function in any society, it scored a pass mark. Since religion is endemic to any human society, ancient and modern, those tools that prop it up and fan the embers of faith in the hearts of its votaries are worth giving attention. One of these tools is the institution of the priesthood. And we shall discuss it from Catholic and traditionalist perspectives. Therefore, in the African traditional setup, religion is almost synonymous with culture. Africans who are notoriously religious who "eat religiously, drink religiously, bathe religiously, dress religiously, and sin religiously."⁵ Cherish, nourish, and sustain the institution of the priesthood as an integral part of their culture.

The role played by the priests during worship in the religions under study is significant, as worship itself has to be orderly, and the one who maintains

¹ D.A. Alsobrook, *Understanding the Blood of Christ*. Kent: Sovereign World Ltd. 1979. 25

² M.F. Asiegbu, *Spiritual Warfare and the Demonization of the other: Missionaries, Pentecostals, Charismatics and the Popular Praxis of Demonology*. *The Nigerian Journal of Theology*, 2006, 20(1), 85-108.

³ R. E. Boylan, *The Priest's Way to God*. Dublin: Scepter Publishing Ltd. 1962, 28

⁴ R.T. Brown, *Priest and Bishop: Biblical Reflections*. London: Geoffrey Chapman. 1971, 12-18.

⁵ D.O. Chukwu, *The Church as the Extended Family of God*. Bloomington, Indiana: Xlibris Publication. 2011, 23-25.

orderliness is the priest. "It is on this note that Aristotle supports the importance of having a priest in every community." This issue of priesthood in religion is what we will discuss in this study, with a particular emphasis on its importance in African Traditional Religion and Christianity. The researcher will also make a comparative study of the concept of the office of priesthood in the two religions.

ANALYSIS OF PRIESTHOOD IN CHRISTIANITY AND AFRICAN TRADITIONAL RELIGION

The Lord commanded every priest to "stand in his own office, and labor in his own calling" (D&C 84:109). To do this, a priest must first learn and then fulfill his different responsibilities in the office assigned to him. As a priest, one has all the duties to ensure that one's office remains a sacred space. In addition, his responsibilities include teaching, baptizing, administering the sacrament, visiting the members, ordaining others to the Aaronic Priesthood, and assisting in missionary work. As he performs these duties, he is not only helping to build the kingdom of God but also preparing himself to receive the Melchizedek Priesthood. When he gets the Melchizedek Priesthood and is ordained to the office of elder, he can be called to serve full-time missions. His effectiveness as a full-time missionary depends on how well prepared he is to serve. He can prepare to be a good missionary by magnifying his callings as a priest.⁶

The Duties of the Priest in Christianity

Worthy brethren may be ordained priests when they are at least 16 years old.

The specific duties of a priest are found in the Doctrine and Covenants.

- Ask the class members to read and mark Doctrine and Covenants 20:46-48. What are the duties of a priest?
- Display a poster of the following duties, or write the information on the chalkboard. We can, as a matter of fact, posit that a priest should appear as a leader and as a servant.

He must be all ready to ensure that he fulfills heavenly mandate, lead the sheep as instructed by God, maintain godly and goodly behavior, and ensure that he stands in the gap between his members and God. He must ensure that orderliness is strictly followed and must be responsible and responsive. It is also a delicate position as he has to battle temptation daily. The following highlights the functions of a priest in Christianity.

⁶ T.D. Adamo, Christianity and the African Traditional Religion(s): The Postcolonial Round of Engagement. Verbum Publishers, Lagos. 2011, 12

Teach the Gospel

One of the duties of a priest is to "preach, teach, expound, exhort" (D&C 20:46). This means that he is to teach others the principles of the gospel. To teach the principles of the gospel, he must first learn what they are. The Lord said, "Seek not to declare my word, but first seek to obtain my word, and then shall your tongue be loosed; then, if you desire, you shall have my Spirit and my word, yea, the power of God unto the convincing of men" (D&C 11:21). We obtain the word of God in several ways. We get it in our homes from our parents, in our priesthood quorums from those who instruct us, in Sunday School, in sacrament meeting, and in seminary and institute classes.⁷

One of the best ways to learn the word of God is through daily personal study of the scriptures. Every priest should make it a habit to study the scriptures regularly. As he searches and ponders the scriptures, the Lord will help us understand them. As we build our knowledge of the gospel, he can teach it to others. He may also fulfill his duty to teach others the gospel through his righteous examples. Many times, our good example encourages others to live the gospel.⁸

Baptize

Show visual 7-a, "A priest may baptize when authorized by the bishop or branch president." Another duty priests have is to baptize (see D&C 20:46). Baptism by the proper authority is one of the most essential and sacred ordinances in the Church, for it is the ordinance by which we become members of the Church, are forgiven of our sins, and enter the path to the celestial kingdom. It is a priest's sacred responsibility to administer this saving ordinance when authorized to do so by the bishop or branch president.⁹

Administer the Sacrament

"Priests have the sacred responsibility of administering the sacrament to the members of the Church." The honor of administering the sacrament is typically reserved for priests, who offer the sacramental prayers. As a priest, one should be familiar with the sacramental prayers, dress appropriately, and wash one's hands before performing this ordinance. Above all, he should be worthy to perform this sacred ordinance as the Savior's representative.¹⁰

⁷ J.O. Akao, The Task of African Theology: Problems and Suggestions. Scriptura 2002, 81:341.

⁸ J.N. Amanze, Christianity and Ancestor Veneration in Botswana. Studies in World Christianity Liberty Publishers, 2003, 8:43.

⁹ A. G. Anderson, Zion and Pentecost: The Spirituality and Experience of Pentecostal and Zionist/Apostolic Churches in South Africa. Pretoria: Unisa Press. 2000, 23

¹⁰ O.J. Awolalu, and P.D. Adelumo, West African Traditional Religion. Ibadan: Onibonjo Press & Book Industries, 1979, 65.

Visit the Members

The Lord has commanded priests to "visit the house of each member, and exhort them to pray vocally and in secret and attend to all family duties" (D&C 20:47). We can accomplish this as we home teach our assigned families. During these visits, we can find out the needs of the family members. He can pray with them¹¹. He can teach them the principles of the gospel and encourage them to attend to their family duties. He can be friendly with the family members in his Church meetings and in the neighborhood. And he can participate with them in Church, school, and community activities¹².

Ordain Others to the Aaronic Priesthood

Priests also have the authority to ordain other priests, teachers, and deacons (D&C 20:48), but only when authorized by the bishop or branch president. This power to confer the Aaronic Priesthood is sacred. It was restored to the earth by John the Baptist when he ordained Joseph Smith and Oliver Cowdery to the Aaronic Priesthood (D&C 13). John the Baptist himself was given authority by an angel acting in the name of God (D&C 84:28). The power to ordain others comes to us, therefore, from God. To perform this critical ordinance, priests should be worthy and have the Holy Ghost with them. (For further information, see lesson 3, "The Restoration of the Priesthood," in this manual.¹³)

Assist in Missionary Work

Show visual 7-c, "Assisting the full-time missionaries is both an obligation and an honor."

The Duties of the Priest in Christianity in Traditional African Religion

- They offered sacrifices on behalf of the communities
- Acted as mediators between God and the people, such as Offering prayers during religious ceremonies, such as birth/initiation/marriage/death/war
- Performed rituals of cleansing/healing
- Reconciling warring parties/peace makers
- They are part of the decision-making body, especially during calamities such as war/epidemics/drought
- Foretell the future/warn people of impending danger/calamities".

¹¹ O.J. Awolalu, Sin and its Removal in African Traditional Religion. Journal of the American Academy of Religion, 1976, 44:275.

¹² G. A. Barker, Christianity: A Guide to Christianity. Oxford: The Subject Centre for Philosophical and Religious Studies, 2005, 89.

¹³ K.M. Bediako, Theology and Identity: The Impact of Culture upon Christian Thought in the Second Century and Modern Africa. Oxford: Regnum Books International, 1992, 23.

Priesthood in African Traditional Religion and in Christianity: Areas of Convergence and Divergence

There is an imminent move towards contextual Christianity in African scholarship. A significant number of African scholars advocate for the contextualization of Christianity, which seeks to establish a connection between African cultural and Christian foundations. But what seems to be lacking in this debate is the critical evaluation of how Christianity can fully be expressed or practiced within the cultural context¹⁴. Even though it is apparent that Africans yearn to experience Christianity within their cultural setting, it remains to be established how Christianity can best be communicated within an African cultural context. So far, the contextualization of Christianity seems to have permitted syncretism. It has resulted in the emergence of “African Christianity”, which is the amalgamation of Christianity and African Traditional Religion (ATR)¹⁵.

The amalgamation of Christianity and African Traditional Religion appears to overlook the essence of both religions, as the elements of one religion are expressed through the other. In this study, the researcher argues that there are “things in between” – *Adiaphora*, which the proponents of contextual Christianity seem to have overlooked about the African cultural and religious heritage. These include the pragmatic nature of African cultural and religious heritage, as well as African traditional methods of healing. Within the modern missiological debate, some scholars contend that the attitude of early missionaries towards the African cultural and religious heritage was often misguided.¹⁶

Early missionaries are accused of being too much involved with their own culture (colonialism included), not understanding much of the African culture, and working hard to destroy what they did not understand. This error, according to Mugambi, resulted in the perception of the Christian identity as equivalent to the Western cultural and religious heritage. Following Western precedence, conversion was determined by behavioral norms, in which African converts had to abandon their traditional African customs and adopt the Western ones. In that context, African converts were forced to live double lives¹⁷.

Mugambi depicts this dichotomy in the following manner: On the one hand, they accepted the norms introduced by the missionaries, who saw nothing valuable in

¹⁴ K.H. Bediako, *Understanding African Theology in the 20th Century*. Themelios, 1994, 20:14.

¹⁵ D.J. Bosch, *Transforming Mission: Paradigm Shifts in Mission Theology*. Maryknoll: Orbis Books, 1991.23.

¹⁶ B.M. Bujo, *Foundations of an African Ethic: Beyond the Universal Claims of Western Morality*. Nairobi: Paulines Publications Africa, 2003.

¹⁷ M.N. Mugambi, *Toward Indigenous Theology in South Africa*. In *Third World Liberation Theologies: A Reader*. Edited by Dean W. Ferm. Maryknoll: Orbis Books, 1986, pp.205.

African culture. On the other hand, the converts could not deny their own cultural identity. They could not substitute their denominational belonging for their artistic and religious heritage. Yet they could not become Europeans or Americans merely by adopting some aspects of the missionaries' outward norms of conduct.¹⁸ The strain of having to live by double standards for African converts led to some difficulties in appreciating the Christian identity. The principal concern was: "What should be the proper relationship between Christian identity and a Christian's cultural identity?". As expected, there were no simple answers to this enquiry. However, suggestions regarding the consideration of inculturation, the reformation or reconstruction of Christianity in Africa, and the Africanization of Christianity seemed more favourable.¹⁹

All these approaches sought to make Christianity more communicative with the African cultural and religious heritage. In this regard, Oden argues that "[m]any African Christians today have a deep conviction that they must think in terms that are indigenously African because this is what has been most neglected". This deep-seated conviction, which tends to lean back to African forms of thought and expression, has become the premise and a solid foundation of African theology²⁰. African theology is the embodiment of the contextualization of Christianity. Muzorewa attests that African theology is an "attempt to respond to a mandate to construct a biblically-based and relevant theology that speaks to the spiritual needs of the African people". Thus, the goal of African theology is to construct a biblically-based and relevant theology that can meet the spiritual needs of African people. The implications, therefore, of African theology are that imported theologies do not sufficiently touch the hearts of African believers because they are couched in a language that is foreign to them. And that the building of communication between Christianity and African cultural and religious heritage is best left to African theologians, as they know how to contextualize Christianity in a manner that fully communicates with their African cultural and spiritual heritage²¹.

Thus, in this argument, Christianity needs to assume a local and Africanized temperament, where it can be communicated in a language that Africans can understand and appreciate, and be articulated in a manner that can touch the hearts of Africans. In its reproduction, it is exclusively the task of African

¹⁸ M.N. Mugambi, African Traditional Religions. In South Africa, Land of Many Religions. Edited by Arno Meiring and Piet Meiring. Wellington: Christian Literature Fund. Evans, Richard G. 2009.

¹⁹ M.N. Mugambi, "Holy Indifference" and "Things Indifferent". Common Knowledge, 2015, 15:23.

²⁰ E.W. Oden, The Quest for an African Christian Theology. The Ecumenical Review, 1975, 27.

²¹ K.L. Fiedler, Christianity and African Culture: Conservative German Protestant Missionaries in Tanzania, 1996, 40.

theologians to contextualize Christianity so that it may fully communicate with the African cultural context. As to how this can be done, it is not clear. But what is apparent is that the contextualization of Christianity has resulted in the emergence of African Christianity²².

African Christianity is the amalgamation of Christianity and African Traditional Religion. It is a form of Christianity that draws from both the Christian faith and African Traditional Religion for some ethico-spiritual principles. It is evidenced by the reverting of Christians back to African traditional practices and the consultation of traditional healers. In this narrative, it becomes difficult for Africans to choose between Christianity and their African conventional practices. Christianity connects them to God while African traditional practices provide a lasting bond with their ancestors. In such a situation, they tend to lack the aspiration to part ways with Christianity and to abandon the ATR totally. According to Mbiti, the other reason why Africans cannot simply choose between Christianity and ATR is that Christianity has been in existence for a very long time in Africa. It has influenced the lives of Africans for so long that “it can rightly be described as an indigenous, traditional and African religion”²³.

The term “African Traditional Religion (ATR)”, in this paper, assumes a singular connotation. This stands against the widespread perception that, as an umbrella term for various African religions, the term should be used in plural²⁴. African scholars like Mbiti initially followed this direction, as he referred to “ATR” in plural (as African religions). He used the term in this manner to account for the diverse beliefs and traditions found in African ethnic groups²⁵. However, Mbiti later revised his position on the second edition: “In the first edition, I spoke about 'African religions' in the plural to keep alive the diversity of African religiosity. I now use the singular, “African religion,” more than the plural expression. The word “traditional” is included “to indicate that these religions emerged among traditional communities in specific regions before they came into contact with other world religions and cultures”. Thus, the use of “ATR” in the singular is perceived to be more approving because it accounts for the common racial origin of Africans and the similarities of their culture and religious beliefs and that the “ATR” should be spoken of in the singular because of the fundamental unity of African religious systems: Although they (African religious systems) were separate and self-contained systems, they interact with one another and influenced

²² I.O. Mbiti, *Sesotho Afrikan Thought and Belief Systems*. 2011, Alberton: Nalane Publication.

²³ I.O. Mbiti, *The Bantu-Speaking Peoples of Southern Africa*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul Publication, 1974, 23

²⁴ I.O. Mbiti, *African Catholicism-An Essay in Discovery*. London: SCM Press, 1989.

²⁵ M.M. Maluleke, *Dreams and Medicines: The Perspective of Xhosa Diviners and Novices in the Eastern Cape, South Africa*. *Indo-Pacific Journal of Phenomenology*, 2005, 5:1-22

one another to different degrees. This justifies our use of the term African Traditional Religion in the singular to refer to the whole African religious phenomenon, even if we are, in fact, dealing with a multiplicity of theologies²⁶.

Thus, the common racial origin of Africans and the similarities in their culture and beliefs deem it appropriate to conceive of the ATR in the singular rather than in plural. Due to the amalgamation of Christianity and ATR, a different form of Christianity has emerged in Africa. It is African Christianity. Since its emergence, scholars like Maluleke²⁷ noted that “the very notion of 'African Christianity' appeared to depict something to be handled with caution and suspicion, if it was not to be rejected altogether”. This is because the very concept of “African Christianity” lacked the requisite history, culture, and theological traditions for Christianity to take on a distinguishable African identity, and the suggestion that Christianity was universal and therefore did not need to be qualified as "African". This implies that the concept of "African Christianity" was, to begin with, uncalled for²⁸.

African Christianity lacks the necessary history, cultural backing, or theological traditions that would distinctly give it an “African” identity. Furthermore, as a universal religion, Christianity cannot simply be reduced to an “African” concept. This may lower the "universal standards" of Christianity and fit it with the local “African standards”²⁹. Thus, the concept of “African Christianity” remains a point of contention in African scholarship. Maluleke further notes that the notion of “African Christianity” is too broad and covers a great scope to be meaningfully examined.³⁰

Scholars such as Ntombana also note that there are professed Christians within the Mainline or Mission Churches, who tend to revert to African traditional practices or consult conventional healers for healing. The falling back of Christians to African traditional practices appears to be a developed phenomenon in Africa. What makes this phenomenon even more disquieting is that some priests or pastors go overboard in becoming traditional healers, while professing to be ‘bona fide’ Christians³¹. To this, scholars such as Mlisa argue that "it is no longer a shame to see a well-educated person or Christian in igqirha's (diviner) regalia or wearing white beads both at church and at work". The acceptance of

²⁶ M.M. Hirst, A River of Metaphors: Interpreting the Xhosa diviner's myth. *Journal of African Studies*, 2007 56: 217

²⁷ M.B. Hunter, *Reaction to Conquest: Effects of Contact with Europeans on the Pondo of South Africa*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1936

²⁸ B.E. Maluleke, *African Traditional Religion: A Definition*. London: SCM Press, 1973

²⁹ E.F. Ntombana, *A History of Christianity in Africa: From Antiquity to the Present*. Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 1995.

³⁰ M.O. Mlisa, *Ubuntu Christianity*. Wellington: Fact and Faith Publications.

³¹ A.F. Jebadu, Ancestral Veneration and the Possibility of its Incorporation into the Christian Faith. *Exchange* 36:246

syncretism by African Christians has become a practical realism in South Africa. This is essentially a result of the contextualization of Christianity in Africa, which has opened doors to syncretism. The primary concern with the contextualization of Christianity in Africa is that African scholars have not adequately considered adiaphora. They have mainly focused on the positive and negative aspects of the African cultural heritage. They tend to elevate the positive and reject the negative²⁵.

The positive aspects include practices such as hospitality, humaneness, respect for God, for life, for ancestors, for elders, or for nature, etc. These are highly encouraged. The negative aspects include practices such as witchcraft, stealing, killing, human sacrifices, disregarding ancestors, interfering with community life, etc.

These are firmly discouraged. In this sense, the contextualization of Christianity in Africa appears to have been mainly concerned with the integration of positive aspects of the African cultural heritage into the Christian faith. This excludes those things that fall “in between”. I refer to these as “adiaphora”²

In conclusion, one crucial fact that warrants mention is the indispensability of the priesthood in the two religions under study. It is worth noting that, in both religions, no successful worship takes place without the latter. In fact, the researcher has not come across any religion that does not rely on the concept of priesthood for its survival. The priesthood in African Traditional Religion and Christianity has played a significant role that deserves the attention of scholars. This, we have done without any equivocation.

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